

TEACHING ENGLISH GRAMMAR THROUGH INTERACTIVE METHODS.

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Abstract. This paper is intended to discuss the main theme teaching English grammar very effectively and in a funny way, to prevent learners from being bored.

Keywords: teaching English grammar, EFL students, innovative methods, intrinsic motivation

Introduction. Grammar is generally thought to be a set of rules specifying the correct ordering of words at the sentence level (Nunan, 2003); Grammar is a description of the rules that govern how a language's sentences are formed (Thornbury, 2008); Grammar «is the way a language manipulates and combines words (or bits of words) in order to form larger units of meaning. (Ur, 1988, p.141). Grammar is undeniably an essential component of effective communication. (Vijayalakshmi, 2014). Ellis (2006) suggests that grammar has kept on holding a central place in EFL teaching.

However, both native and second-language speakers get difficulties in learning English grammar since there are a great number of intricate, obscure, and exceptional grammatical rules (Macfadyen, 2015). EFL students find this aspect of language the most difficult. (Ahmad, 2018).

Indeed, one may know all the words in a sentence and yet fail to understand it, if one does not see the relationship between the words in the given sentence. No speaking is possible without the knowledge of grammar, without the forming of a grammar mechanism. Grammar is something that produces the sentences of a

language. Correct selection of grammar teaching material is the first step towards the elimination of mistakes.

The grammar lessons at the secondary schools have the unfortunate reputation of being boring. They rely on traditional presentation methods, using the textbook and generalized fill-in-the-blanks exercises (Fischer, 2012). The study of grammar has only enhanced knowledge about the English language but does not facilitate learners of EFL on how to use the language. This theoretical knowledge of the rules of grammar, however, is not going to be of any help for the learners. Instead, the students should be taught to understand how to use the grammar rules in a communicative situation. (Vijayalakshmi, 2014).

Methods. Here you can find some innovative and also interactive methods for teaching EFL students:
1. *Learning grammar through games.* Games help and encourage many learners to sustain their interest and work. Games also help teachers to create contexts in which the language is useful and meaningful. The theory of intrinsic motivation also gives some insight as to why teaching grammar through games actually works. Intrinsic motivation refers to the internal factors that encourage us to do something. Most young learners will not internally decide that they want to learn grammar. They don't yet understand the concepts of why it's important to know proper grammar, so these external factors won't affect them much either. Instead, Intrinsic motivation can lead encourage them to play games. If these games are good then they will be learning while they are playing.

2. *Using songs and poems.* Songs are one of the most enhancing and culturally rich resources that can easily be used in language classrooms. They are resourceful tools to enhance the learner's abilities in listening, speaking, reading and writing. Learning English grammar through songs provides an enjoyable and relaxing classroom atmosphere for the learners. They may encourage extensive and intensive listening, and inspire creativity and use of imagination in the relaxed classroom atmosphere.

Similar to songs, poems have an enormous linguistic value as they provide authenticity and cultural views. Poems contextualize a grammar lesson effectively. They serve as an effective tool for practicing a specific grammatical structure, in particular, a poem that exemplifies a particular structure, such as jazz chants.

3. *Tasks and storytelling.* Task- Based Language Teaching (henceforth TBLT) is one of these methods and deals with grammar teaching through communicative use of the language. Essentially, it tries to let learners use the language effectively. Learning grammar can be used by assigning tasks.

Everyone loves a story. Stories form a very integral part of teaching language. They provide a realistic context for presenting grammar points. It can be used for both eliciting and illustrating grammar points. Storytelling is traditional and pervasive in almost all cultures.

Conclusion. Using innovative methodologies, such as: games, storytelling, songs, effective tasks in teaching English grammar in the classroom will pave a positive way to students to learn the language effectively. If teachers teach their students in effective ways through fun and relaxation, the students will be able to learn grammar very fast and they can find each rule of English grammar very interesting.

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